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ASPECTS OF ADVERTISING - A CROSS-CULTURAL STUDY

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ABSTRACT

This research paper tries to analyze and compare different Indian & U.S. based advertisements which have created an impact on the society or else have tried to enlighten the society for its betterment. It judges the advertisements on different parameters and their elements, so as to recognize the aspects and constraints of the society and the cultural differences existing between U.S.A. and India which make various advertisements with social appeals successful or unsuccessful.

Keywords: Advertisements, Impact, society.

Research Paper: Aspects of Advertising - A Cross-Cultural Study

Advertisements do play a significant role in shaping the society and do create long lasting impacts on the society. There have been enumerative instances of such kind of advertisements that have not only influenced the society but have really contributed in bringing a positive change in it. We carried out a qualitative research was carried out on the impact making 100 advertisements of India and 100 advertisements of U.S.A. which carried social messages.

The advertisements which we have analyzed were compared on various terminologies like:

- Audio Acts - Directive Speech, Expressive Speech, Informational Speech, Poetic Speech
- Visual Effects – use of iconic characters, indexical value transfer, use of iconic image of women
- Combined use of Verbal & Visual Effects

We compared all the advertisements carrying social message under our sample list on the basis of various parameters. The first thing that we did was analyzing them on the bases of the types of information provided by such ads where in the results that we got are as follows:

Type of Information provided by the ad	US Ads	Indian Ads
New Ideas	6%	7%
Availability Information	10%	80%
Special Dates / Offers	7%	6%
Company Research	19%	8%
Safety	13%	13%
Outcome Based	56%	43%
Website Address	52%	13%
Quality / Performance	89%	90%

More or else on most of the parameters of Information cues the results are almost the same for both India & U.S. except for a few differences like Website address which is found very important in U.S. and not equally important in India where availability date was a more important information cue. Whereas as quality/performance holds equal importance in both U.S. and India. For the other information parameters or cues the importance ratings were found to be almost same.

Various Important Elements of an Advertisement:

Ideally and advertisement is said to have the following five elements:

- Heading
- Sub-Heading
- Tagline / Punchline / Business Line / Logo
- Image
- Body Copy

An analysis was carried out on the sorted out 100 Indian Ads & 100 U.S. Ads carrying social messages to judge the level of emphasis laid on each element in both the countries:

Elements	India Advertisements (with a social message)	U.S. Advertisements (with a social message)
Heading	30%	89%
Sub-Heading	18%	57%
Tagline / Punchline / Business Line	100%	100%
Image	100%	100%
Bodycopy	21%	77%

Basically American Advertisement that were created always run on the common school of thought of Minimalist Advertising. As lifestyle in America is quite different and faster than that of India. Time being a constraint in U.S. lifestyle all the social ads in U.S. scored low in Heading, Sub-Heading and Bodycopy. The other reasons for this kind of a result was that an average American is bombarded with more number of Ads everyday almost 250 as compared to an average Indian.

On the other hand the literacy level in India is quite low Image and Body copy both score high including Headings this can be attributed to the High context culture in India whereas Americans possess a low context culture. So Image is important in American Ads so as to increase the advertising recall because in U.S. people require brief and precise information whereas in India it is more important because of illiteracy where people require more information and pictorial representations make it easier to understand and remember.

Verbal Effects used in Advertising:

Mostly advertisements use three kinds of speech acts: Expressive, Directive & Poetic. Our analysis revealed that the U.S. based ads more often use Expressive Verbal Effects. The results have revealed that 69% of the U.S. ads use expressive speech while only 42% of the Indian ads used Expressive approach. As we have already mentioned that due to the high contextual nature of the Indian ads most of the social ads have used Poetic approach. And owing to the low contextual nature of American Ads it was found that they have been using more Direct verbal effects.

Verbal Effects	Indian Ads	US Ads
Expressive Verbal Approach	42%	69%
Directive Verbal Approach	63%	41%
Poetic Verbal Approach	11%	89%

Use of Women in Advertisements:

In this research it has also been found in the research that the US based ads have been projecting women more as an economically independent & liberated personality and in Indian Social Advertisements Women are now shown in two types of categories one as the more educated and socially responsible and the other in a stereotypic role. Owing to the societal hazards that India faces where still people have to be enlightened about basic hygiene, polio drops, educating girls a lot of advertisements have been created where mostly we find a women presented as an iconic personality who delivers the social message for e.g. the Vidya Balan advertisements where she explains the importance of construction of toilets in the houses with the punch line “Jahan Soch wahan Shouchalaya”. T.V. commercials as well as radio jingles have been created for the same. The use of Women as a homemaker or in other stereotypic roles is also seen more in Indian Ads created for spreading social awareness.

Projection of Women	Indian Ads	U.S. Ads
Women in Stereotypical Role	63%	19%
Women as Economically Independent and Liberated personality	89%	42%
Neutral form	25%	9%

Strategies to Attract Readers:

This research also analyzed the strategies used by various Indian and U.S. Advertisements to attract the attention of audience. In case of Indian Social Ads they still rely on the negative tactics to scare the target audience. They also use Emotional appeal to a very high extent as compared to the rational appeals which are more common in U.S. based social ads. Similarly comparative arguments are seen more in American Ads.

Analysis of Results & Interpretations:

Presentation of Collectivistic v/s Individualistic Values:

It was found to be of high importance to analyze the values that are portrayed in the advertisements of both the Indian and American Ads. Any kind of social ad appeals to its target audience only if the target can relate themselves to characters and values portrayed in the advertisements. Collectivism and family values are more in the high contextual Indian cultures whereas Individualism is more in Low Context American culture. That is why any Indian Social Welfare Advertisement is found to be based on relationships and family values whereas in American ads individualistic approach is more dominant due to the lifestyle of America.

The American Ads mostly carry lesser content hence we found that only web address is placed for more information whereas in Indian ads a lot of content is placed. The research depicts that in there were significant differences in Indian Social Advertisements and American Ads but ofcourse with a lot of similarities which could have varied reasons for e.g. the use of images was extensive in both the countries because of different reasons.

33% of Indian population comprises of audience between 0-14 years and 30% are between 15-25 years which means that India will remain young till 2060. This justifies the use of Celebrities more often in Indian Advertisements whereas as per the demographics American population consists of Aging & elderly target audience. Celebrities & Indian Stars are looked upon as the “Demi – Gods” as compared to US where the aging population likes the use of Politicians and writers in advertisements. The same reason also justifies the reason of use of more children and cartoons in India whereas American ads use more of elderly people.

Similarly another finding of this study is the fact that Americans ads involve more use of rational arguments and humor along with the use of comparative arguments whereas Indian ads depend on emotional appeals and the insecurities a citizen could carry.

Indians are very traditional & ritualistic and that is why India ads use vibrant colors like red, yellow, saffron , green which are considered auspicious in India. On the other hand American ads use black color more than others as it is considered as the symbol of power & dominance and more often American Ads use more sober & subtle colors.

This study provides an insight to the significance of social advertisements in India as well as U.S.. From a realistic point of view the results of this study show the similarities and dissimilarities between the characteristics & rudiments of advertisements of both the countries. From a sociological point of view this study provides an insight to the portrayal & projection of women in social advertising based on the societal norms and cultures of both the countries. From a professional point of view this research study has answered a lot of queries which any advertiser faces while creating international ad campaigns. Hence this study clearly suggests the use of localized measures for effective advertising. It gives a cross cultural study for the ease of out sourcing of advertising to the other regions or for International brands for targeting other countries.

Hence for any marketer or advertiser it is very important to have a clear cultural understanding of the targeted nation so as to devise a significantly effective localized solution for advertising. Hence in today’s competitive advertising arena localized approach is very important for any international advertiser.

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